

THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN ENGLISH AND GERMAN

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ANNOTATION

This article presents that no one can deny that English and German are two widely used languages. While the former is a global language, the latter is second only to English in terms of number of speakers globally, with over 100 million speakers across every continent. If you want to learn German, now is the perfect time due to globalization and high demand in the competitive job market. However, you may think that this is a difficult job but it is not. If you speak English fluently, you will have no difficulty learning and mastering German. However, if you are a beginner, the process will be gradual. We've compiled a list of similarities between English and German, especially for you.

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Similarities Between English and German

Here are some common similarities between English and German. Check them out! Both are Germanic languages. The most important thing to remember is that English is a language that evolved from West Germanic about 2,000 years ago. Indeed, German and English are considered part of the Germanic branch of the Indo-European language family, implying that they remain closely related to each other today. Given their common ancestors, it's not surprising that they have striking similarities. It is estimated that more than a third of non-technical English vocabulary, as well as many English words, are of German origin. In addition, Latin, Greek and French vocabulary was borrowed from existing languages.

Same alphabets

One of the most obvious similarities between German and English is that both languages use the same 26 letters of the Latin alphabet. This is a significant advantage because it allows English speakers to start writing in German immediately. This change is quite simple, except for the rules for learning the additional umlaut letters (ä, ö and

ü) and the Eszett or sharp S (ß). This is undeniably an advantage for English speakers trying to learn a language like Mandarin, Arabic or Japanese, which use a completely different writing system.

Same grammatical rules

One trait that English speakers who attempt to learn German may notice is a similarity in grammatical rules. The verb 'to drink', which is 'trinken' in German, is perhaps the best example of this.

The English term changes depending on the tense, from 'drink' to 'drank' to 'drunk'. In German, you use the words 'trinkt', 'trank', and 'getrunken' for the same three tenses, and the same general pattern applies to most other verbs as well. As a result, an English speaker can typically have a solid sense of German verb patterns right away.

Arabic Numbering Systems

Another benefit of studying German as an English speaker is that the two languages share the same Arabic numbers and numbering system. Numbers, like in English, are made up of sequences of the digits 0-9, and while these numerals have distinct names in German, they all follow the same basic principles.

This is likely best demonstrated by examining the numbers from 10 to 20.

English: ten, eleven, twelve, thirteen, fourteen, fifteen, sixteen, seventeen, eighteen, nineteen, and twenty in English.

German: zehn, elf, zwölf, dreizehn, vierzehn, fünfzehn, sechzehn, siebzehn, achtzehn, neunzehn, zwanzig.

The suffix 'teen' is substituted with 'zehn', but the essential pattern remains the same. In general, this is an application of discourse analysis at a much broader text level, rather than a sentence or a word. Most linguists agree to classify text into five types: narrative, descriptive, argumentative, informative, and compare/contrast. Some taxonomies divide text types according to their functions.

SUMMARY COMPLETION: In this article, I have described Examining these cognates proves it beyond a shadow of a doubt: In terms of common words, German and English have a lot in common. Between the two languages that have a history of borrowing from each other, you can discover the same exact words, similar variations, or even distinct meanings of the same spelling. If you speak one of these languages,

now is the time to learn the other! These related terms will hasten the absorption process tenfold! And if you ever get confused, you can refer to this blog!

REFERENCES

1. Abduraxmanova, Z., & Mamurova, M. (2021). THEORETICAL APPROACH TO SPEECH DISFLUENCIES IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION. In *МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ* (pp. 43-45).

2. 1. Parmonova, N. (2022). Nasiba THE PHENOMENON OF CONVERSION IN ENGLISH: THE PHENOMENON OF CONVERSION IN ENGLISH.

3. 2. Kuznetsova S. The use of the project methods at the lessons of English. – 2014 pp.12 – 13. – Text: electronic. – URL:

4. <https://nsportal.ru/shkola/inostrannyeyazyki/>

5. [angliiskiy-yazyk/library/2014/02/22/statya-metod-proektov-v-obuchenii](https://nsportal.ru/shkola/inostrannyeyazyki/angliiskiy-yazyk/library/2014/02/22/statya-metod-proektov-v-obuchenii)

6. 3. Lectures on the Theory and methodology of teaching a foreign language

Text:

7. electronic. – URL: [https://infourok.ru/lekcii-po-teorii-i-metodikeobucheniyainostrannomu-](https://infourok.ru/lekcii-po-teorii-i-metodikeobucheniyainostrannomu-yaziku-481575.html)

8. [yaziku-481575.html](https://infourok.ru/lekcii-po-teorii-i-metodikeobucheniyainostrannomu-yaziku-481575.html)